

ANALYTICAL STUDY ON UNEMPLOYMENT AMONG PROFESSIONALLY QUALIFIED WOMEN IN MALAPPURAM DISTRICT

Naseema P

Assistant Professor, ISS College of Teacher Education, Perinthalmanna

☎ 83010 43061 | ✉ naseemajaleeltvr@gmail.com

Dr. Irshana Shahnaz Ulladan

Assistant Professor, Farook Training College, Calicut

☎ 97443 66986 | ✉ irshana07@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID: AJSCS-691D77B4D2378

Received: 2025-10-21

Published: 2025-11-20

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17662988>

Page No: 771-790

Abstract

Education is important for everyone irrespective of gender, socio-economic status, or caste differences. It is not just a matter of self-dependency or self-respect but it empowers each individual for more. Education empowers women just as men to come forward and contribute towards the development and prosperity of the country. Holistic empowerment and independence can be achieved only through proper education and employment of women. The state of Kerala in India is known for its high literacy rates. But contradictorily, the percentage of female employment in Kerala is amongst the lowest in the nation and in Kerala, unemployment among women is highest in Malappuram district in contrast to the other districts (Arun, 2017). This paper is an attempt to find out the causes behind the educated unemployment especially from professionally qualified unemployed women of Malappuram district. Analytic induction technique was used to analyse causes and solutions among qualified unemployed women using open-ended questionnaire. Results of the data disclosed the causes and solutions of educated unemployment among professionally qualified women from their perspectives.

Keywords: - Professionally qualified unemployed women, causes of unemployment.

Cite This Paper: NASEEMA. P and Dr. Irshana Shahnaz Ulladan (2025). "ANALYTICAL STUDY ON UNEMPLOYMENT AMONG PROFESSIONALLY QUALIFIED WOMEN IN MALAPPURAM DISTRICT ". *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SUSTAINABLE CITY AND SOCIETY (AJSCS)*, vol. 15, no. 2, 2025, pp. 771-790. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17662988>

Introduction

Education is important for personal, social and economic development of the nation. Education guides human to fight survival challenges and achieve success in life (Duarte, 2016). It is the only way to eradicate unemployment, and many other problems. Education is not just about getting degree; it is about ensuring happiness and prosperity.

Higher educational qualification gives opportunity to succeed in today's global economy. Modern universities provide their students with various programs aimed at preparing them for different economic sectors. Higher levels of educational attainment lead to higher earnings and lowers unemployment among both men and women. Through continuing education, career-minded individuals can constantly improve their skills and become more proficient at their jobs.

Education is synonymous to increase in productivity along with knowledge and skill enhancement. Education also plays a prominent role in economy as it is assumed that it would lead to employment. In case of women employability, accessibility, ownership, development and empowerment is the expected outcome. This financial independency will create independence in decision-making, a greater autonomy of one's being. This changed situation will further strengthen women's social and economic position in the family and in the community.

Moreover, education helps in transformation. It is well said that educating a boy means educating a single man but educating a girl means educating the whole family. Today, our government is working hard to educate more women and simultaneously investing a huge amount of money on girl child so that that they can be educated. This is because "when a woman thrives, all of the society benefits", and when a society is benefited it creates a true positive impact on our nation (Arjumand, 2016).

Financial independence is amongst the most important factor that controls the quality of a woman's life. It is one of the most liberating aspects that can lead to a quality life with respect. When women are financially stable, they can bear their own expenses, they do not need to seek money from their partner. Earning money will give them a sense of accomplishment and self-identity; it allows evolving as a better and independent human being. Being engaged at home alone, women often suffer a feeling of guilt, they might feel ashamed asking for money from their

husbands, fathers, brothers or sons. However, when women start to earn, they are supposed to be entitled the freedom to spend whatever and wherever they want.

Working women with a successful career enjoy a good life where she has an array of sources to find positive reinforcement outside the home. Working outside the home helps women to maintain and develop their sense of self. Working outside home or doing a job, allows them to connect with different people from diverse backgrounds. Interacting with different people opens their mind and broadens their perspectives.

Working women have a life beyond their family and kids, which gives them a sense of self-accomplishment and fulfilment. Their self-esteem increases considerably as they feel satisfied with themselves. A woman should have a choice to do a job or not to. Like men, women also have the right to work and no one is allowed to refuse this right to her. Employers should take a wise step to bring gender equality at workplace (Reddy, 2016).

Looking at the literacy rate of India in 2011 was 74.04%. However, there is noticeably discrepancy in the literacy rates of men and women. Nation wide, the male literacy rate is 82.14% and Female literacy rate is 65.46% , while the figures in the state of Kerala are 96.11% and 91.07% according to Census of Government of India, 2011.

In the state of Kerala, professional gross enrolment ratio in women is 79.5 but in men, it is only 53.2. However, in the case of work force women ratio is very less than men. Kerala has the highest female unemployment rate in the country according to various rounds of NSSO surveys on employment and unemployment. The NSSO data for 2011-12 indicates that the overall unemployment rate in Kerala is 6.7 with a wide gender gap of 14.1 per cent for women and 2.9 per cent for men (Social Statistics at a Glance, 2016). Furthermore, according to NSSO 68th round data, the widest gender gap in worker population ratio in rural and urban areas was observed in Malappuram district, the most populous in the state.

Hence the present study is an attempt to qualitatively explore into the causes and possible solutions for unemployment among the professionally qualified women in Malappuram district from their perspective.

Title of the Study

The present study is entitled as “CAUSES OF UNEMPLOYMENT AMONG PROFESSIONALLY QUALIFIED WOMEN IN MALAPPURAM DISTRICT”

Objective

To identify the causes of unemployment among professionally qualified women for the total sample and the subgroups- teachers, doctors and engineers.

Methodology

A constant comparison method using Analytic induction technique was used to analyse causes and solutions among professionally qualified unemployed women. Participants were asked to complete an open-ended questionnaire in regards to unemployment among professionally qualified women. Category construction of responses was based upon inductive analysis, allowing for the comparison of one response to the previous one for similarity or difference.

Sample

Using the snowball purposive sampling, the investigator collected data from 100 professionally qualified women. The sample includes sixty-six women teachers, twenty-nine women engineers and five women doctors from Malappuram district.

Tool

Open Ended Questionnaire on Unemployment among Professionally Qualified Women

Analysis and Discussion

Part 1: Causes of Unemployment among Professionally Qualified Women

Most of the professionally qualified women were facing many issues related to being employed. The responses were categorized concerning personal causes of unemployment among professionally qualified women, physical causes, social causes, cultural causes, professional causes. These causes of unemployment among professionally qualified women distinguished as list of causes and category construction was made and shown in Table 1.

Table 1

List of Causes and Category Construction

Personal Causes in Unemployment (P.C)
Family Problems.
Laziness.
Lack of Interest.
Lack of Enquiry.
Lack of Confidence.
Lack of Support from Family/ Husband.
Elder Sisters are Staying at Home.
Outside with Husband.
Physical Causes (PH.C)
Caring of Children's.
Pregnancy.
Lack of Transportation Facility.
Social Causes (S.C)
Gender Inequality.
Lack of Security.
Pay Inequality
Norms of Society.
Cultural Causes (C.C)
Orthodox Thinking like, Family did not Need Women's Income to Survive.
Professional Causes (PF.C)
Lack of Professional Skill.
Lack of Job Vacancy.
Lack of Job in Nearest Place
Less Salary.
Time Schedule.
Lack of Opportunity.
Lack of Experience.
Lack of Accommodation.
More Interest in Youth Icons.
Less Scope.
Stress

The investigator coded each of these in connection to the list of causes obtained through data collection. Based on this coding the investigator inductively analysed the responses by constant comparison. The analysis reveals many causes of unemployment among professionally qualified women, which includes; Personal causes (P.C), Physical causes (PH.C), Social causes (S.C), Cultural causes (C.C), and Professional causes (PF.C). Each of the categories are explained in detail as follows:

Personal Causes of Unemployment (P.C)

- **Family Problems**

Balance between work and family forms an important element to everyone. While the researcher read the data, some conflicts could be noted between the work and family domains were found. They are:

- (a) Time consumed by one-role results in the lack for the other,
- (b) Strain caused by one of the roles makes it difficult to fulfil the responsibilities of other, or
- (c) In-role behaviour, one domain is incompatible with the other domain.

The time-conflict is obvious and probably most salient to the people (i.e., non-work family conflict experts). People are stressed-out at their works; they may not be able to deal with their family responsibilities and vice versa. It has been suggested that the people may sometimes behave in ways that one domain is incompatible with the other domain. For instance, being a perfectionist may be useful at work, but the same behaviours may lead to less effective parenting or in other ways inhibit one from adequately fulfilling their family responsibilities. Work-family conflict results in a number of dysfunctional outcomes, including burnout, decrease in mental well-being, deteriorating relationships, job and life dissatisfaction. Some of the things that lead to conflict are intuitive. For example, working for long hours, long commutes to and from work, workload, lack of management support, job involvement, and level of importance assigned to one's work, marital status, children, and level of importance assigned to family roles, and lack of family support all contribute to it. Family responsibilities are the basic duties involved in a family such as taking care of other family members. Children in a family require care from their parents or guardians, and this has posed a challenge to employees to balance this with the work demands. This has been a

major cause of work-family stress and is mainly determined by the number of children in a family. Familial responsibilities have always been a source of conflict between work and family. Some people believe that when someone has multiple roles, the result would be role-conflict or overload. The role conflict occurs when an employee's tries to meet and satisfy the work demands and family responsibilities at the same time. Work-family role conflict is an inter-role conflict that occurs because the roles of work on one hand and family on the other are not compatible.

- **Laziness**

While cross checking the data, the investigator found people who are not desperate to find jobs even if they have some opportunities. The investigator thinks that around 1% of population is truly lazy. They are not ready to do any work. The people of workforce have no path forward. That likely makes them demotivated, which leads to laziness. Moreover, some people have lived with a belief that they do not fit to be employed and thereby they do not opt for trying to get a job. However, in the case of some women; they have enough money inherited from their either rich husband or affluent parents. While some have the tendency to abstain from work, because they are lazy to do work. Whereas, some people even cannot think about the job because of family responsibility along with it, which also leads to laziness.

- **Lack of Interest**

Most of the people from whom data was collected reported they have lack interest in doing their professional work. After getting degree and master degree in their own subject area, they are truly indolence. The investigator thinks the lack of interest emerges from procrastination, I believe is simply the result of fear, which clouds our decision that fails to take action and hence put off on things. Alternatively, it may be the lack of passion; passion is something that inspires us towards a goal or vision that we look forward to achieving or having in our life. On other hand, workload leads to wage pressure, which leads to reduce the interest to do their job, while they feel job is burden. In case of women, we know these all things definitely affect their employment since their primary focus is on family. Moreover, the workload of family and job creates extreme confusion for them to select for their convenience. This thing reduces their interest to do work properly. In addition, the number of children reduces their interest in going for a job because they want to prioritize caring for their children. Otherwise, the mother thinks that herchildren will not get much

love and affection from them. All these issues reduce their interest to do their job in an appropriate manner.

- **Lack of Enquiry**

Some of the women are not searching for a job in their own field. Especially married ones, they are not ready do and search for jobs. The lazy people are also included in this category. They think job will come to them. These types of people are not in a position to accept the low-level jobs in their field. Nevertheless, they do not try to find out other suitable jobs. These people have no goal or aim. If they have any aim or goal to do the job, they will surely be searching for a job.

- **Lack of Confidence**

Almost all women have low self-esteem and lack of confidence in spite of being highly educated and talented. However, at some point in their lives, they may get a negative feedback or situation to undermine their self-esteem and that has continued to affect their performance and success every day. May be the lack of confidence is different for each person. Each person's cultural background, childhood experience, and other life circumstances all play a role. These things are the obstacles to do a job. It is the cause of abstinence from their professional job. Due to the lack of confidence, women often stand back in being employed. In case of women, they cannot survive even a small bad incident from their higher employees or superior officers. Sometime women cannot adjust with those incidents. While comparing men and women, women have less confidence than men. This could be the reason behind the low-hearted mind of women. In addition, women often have to take a break from the professional job, sometimes, which makes it difficult to update their job, and this mounts to being less confident and hence backward in their employment. In addition, the achievement of others will affect the stability of the person. It leads to less confidence. For being a successful employee, she should have high level of confidence.

- **Lack of Support from Family/ Husband**

Some of the sample reported that having a support from family would make the strength to make a person do anything. Family support is the pillar to do work with satisfaction. Without family support, work may be highly burden and may not be able to concentrate efficiently at work. If people going to work without family support women, have to hear the scuffle from home and

from work. It reduces the mental power and physical power to do work. When the family does not allow women to go for a job, they would feel unhappy, disappointed and frustrated. In the male dominated society, most of the women are not allowed to do work. Their thinking is very narrow. Lack of family support will decrease employee's job satisfaction. Lack of family support is the cause of the high unemployment. Due to the daily scuffling from family, it decreases the interest in job. Orthodox family prefers to reject their women from working. The elder members of family are no ready to send their women for any job. Another thing that matters is, to seek permission from the husband before going out or doing anything without knowledge. Mostly the men do not prefer their wives going out to work, as they have to be kept satisfied with the household chores.

- **Elder Sisters are Staying at Home**

From the data, this cause was very eye catching. This cause usually affects only after the marriage. It just means that if there is any elder daughter in law who is educated and not going for work, then the younger ones too cannot be going for work. It can be found that most of these occur not only in Muslim community but in other communities too, especially after marriage. It may be the selfish mentality and narrow thinking about oneself. It reduces the chance to do something in their subject area. In addition, "Self" is an egocentric cause. It obstacles one's freedom to do work.

- **Outside with Husband**

Another cause that has been found is of women staying abroad with their husband. Most of the women are living with their husband abroad. They have no chance to work and some are not ready to work even if they are highly educated. Moreover, they think their husband's earning is enough to live with. Actually, through this the people are deceiving the government by getting education free of cost in which the government spends lakh of money for each student. Nevertheless, after getting the degree those persons truly spoil it without using the opportunities. This is not only the problem of women, but husbands also. Because they are not ready to send them for any work. Maybe it makes them feel shy of their husband. Society thinks women are only for caring the children, husband and their family. Therefore, job is the major hurdle to manage these. So, women stay back confined at home.

Physical Causes of Unemployment (PH.C)

- **Caring of Children's**

Some of the women reported childcare is necessary for parents-particularly mothers. As per the reason they cannot go to the work. Over the past two decades, the cost of payment towards day-care is higher than the salary they receive. As a result, some decide to leave the workforce. If the child number may increase, again it is an issue for parents. They cannot hire the house cleaner. Therefore, they are ready to leave their job. Moreover, they believe mothers are the best to care own children. Lack of childcare facilities lead to fear of employment. During the early ages of a child, they need to be more cared by mothers. To baby-sit is one of the major risks of unemployment.

- **Pregnancy**

Pregnancy can be one of the other causes of unemployment. While pregnancy women face some health issues and need more relaxation. Therefore, at that time they prefer to resign from their job. After the birth of child, they spend most of time for taking care of the child and continually they have less touch in their profession. Thus, they slowly begin to hesitate going to work. Gradually they completely hold back in their profession. Apart from some women have shy to face their co-employers with her protruded belly. And the orthodox thinking like while pregnancy women need calm and quit atmosphere and she should engage with hearing music's and reading holy books that will affect the mental and physical growth of the baby. Therefore, the parents and elders from the family encourage her to stop her work on the temporary basis. Moreover, travelling limits for the wellness of her health. These all reasons lead to the causes of unemployment among professionally qualified women.

- **Lack of Transportation Facility**

Lack of transportation is one of the other major causes of unemployment. Especially the late-night travelling is very difficult for women. It does not ensure the security of women. Moreover, increasing distance from home to office will make travelling difficulty. Maybe she would have to depend upon one or two buses and auto to reach her destination. It will make her

exhausted. Moreover, often women would have her household chores left which would make her day off.

Social Causes of Unemployment (S.C)

- **Gender Inequality**

Gender inequality exists in workplace. It is a type of sex discrimination, which results in a particular individual being treated disadvantageously because of their gender. It is something, which has emerged out of skewed perceptions and socially constructed roles for each gender. In the workplace, it is common for most women to encounter some form of gender bias. However, many companies try to make pointed efforts to encourage diversity and equality. Nevertheless, none of that changes a simple fact that women still occupy lower paying positions and consistently earn less than their male counterparts earn. Women continue to push through gender barriers and more and more of them are choosing careers in traditionally male dominated fields such as technology and engineering. Yet, for all of their efforts, women still are recognized and rewarded less than men. This gender bias is unfair. Providing separate bathrooms in an office for males and females is an example of the two sexes being treated differently. When hiring decisions, or decisions related to promotion or continued employment are based on an employee's gender, then they are being treated unequally and unfairly. In some jobs, travelling is necessary and employees may even have to relocate different locations either in the country or internationally. For women, some of these things can be problematic. For instance, relocating might not be possible due to their spouse's work. In addition, there is necessarily a limit to how much time some women can put in at work, especially if they have families, the amount of time they can devote to their job may not be considered enough for them to get the same benefits as men. Therefore, gender inequality is a serious cause among women unemployment.

- **Lack of Security**

Today the rules and regulations are supporting to women, but that is only in printed medias. Women are not safe at night, as they cannot travel alone in our society. We know from the news report that often while returning from office they mistreated and often brutally raped. Due to lack of proper security arrangements by the company, women specially working in night shifts have

become victims of rapes and sexual harassments. Male employee assaulting women workers in office transport has been reported every second of a day. These types of incidents make the women to restrict their jobs and it reduces the interest to do the jobs. Moreover, another thing is sexual the harassment at the work place. It may be verbal or physical.

- **Pay Inequality**

It is one of the most major issues that women employees have to face at their workplace. Most of the time despite of being more proficient and qualified than fellow male employees, women workers are paid less than males for the same amount of work. Women are still considered worthy to get low pay and their effort and hard work are undermined in front of male co-workers. Even sometimes along with pay inequity, they face discrimination respect of recruitment, salary hike, and positions up-gradation and, many more. Women are highly discriminated and men always get an upper-edge compared to women during recruitment. In spite of having all the required qualification, talent and expertise, women find it difficult to be selected for a position as several concepts like women are emotional, they are physically and mentally weak, cannot give sufficient time, maternity issues and several other things come in the way.

- **Norms of Society**

Restrictions placed on women's social interactions and freedom of movement, control over household finances and they are bearing responsibility for household chores and childcare. Moreover, women do not have the freedom to travel alone at night. Apart from anything, for most duty of the women is to care their family. Women can only do the simple jobs like sweeping, cleaning, washing like that; she cannot do the duty of an engineer, doctor. Parents are worried about girls. Because, at the time of puberty parents want to conduct the marriage of them, even if they have not well educated and well employed. Women are only for altruism and self-sacrifice.

Cultural Causes of Unemployment (C.C)

- **Orthodox Thinking like, Families do not Need Women's Income to Survive**

This cause is familiar in ordinary and rich families. In some families their husband and family members may very rich, may be the daughter or wife are well educated. However, the elder

member of the family tells them not to go to job; as they have enough money to live. Therefore, she is asked to stay at home and care the members of the family. Another thing is some aged people think women's work is only to care her children's and husband.

Professional Causes of Unemployment (PF.C)

- **Lack of Professional Skills**

An individual professional skill is extremely an important ingredient in any job. The way someone incorporates, handle their workload, and act around the office can determine their success or failure as an employee. Now days, most of the professional have the highly certified mark sheets but they are very weak in case of leading the job, handling the risky situation and cooperating with others. Some of the samples established, it widely seen in women. May be the reason is their family pressure and maybe they are carrying much responsibility in their family. As per the reasons they cannot work efficiently.

- **Lack of Job Vacancy**

Today, job is like a competition. All the youth around us are well educated but they have not much jobs near them. In addition, have so many professional courses, but the demand of such courses is comparatively less in the native areas, but probability of job outside would not be practical for the women. Rising of the retirement age is another problem of lack of job vacancy. Teachers and engineers are very much in number. Hence, availability of job turns a big question to all. As we see, the ratio of job is very less in comparison to the number of people who have qualified competitive exams.

- **Lack of Job Vacancy in Nearest Place**

Women always like to do job at their nearest. As it would help them keep a balance between work and family. However, the availability of such works turns out of luck and if not creates confusion in the minds.

- **Less Salary**

Women are paid less because management had a present notion that she will leave the job after having children or marriage. While harassment, bullying etc. are vivid acts in offices, the

lower pay scale is something that kills the confidence of a female employee from inside. It is a silent crime and no one can complain about it. Women should be vocal about their right, remaining silent means that you are also supporting the shameful act. Men should not be paid more for performing a particular job just because they are men. The equal pay act of 1963 made it a federal requirement that pay scales for identical work be the same regardless of whether the employee doing the labor is male or female. If a woman works the same hours, performs the same tasks, and is required to meet the same goals as her male counterpart, she is entitled to equal pay. When women are paid less because of their gender.

- **Time Schedule**

Comparing men, women cannot do their work at night. Because most of the office's women are not secure. Moreover, they have the responsibility of caring their family. Therefore, they want to reach their home on time. Distance between home and office is another issue, if the duration increases then it is hard to travel to their home. Typically, the orthodox mind-set in the society makes it difficult for a working woman to balance her domestic environment with the professional life. In some families, it may not be acceptable to do work after six'o clock. Those families that do accept these working hours may experience considerable anxiety every day about women's safety while travelling. So many issues affect a working woman because she is closely protected or watched by her family and the society.

- **Lack of Opportunity**

Comparing to men, women have less opportunity in the working field. Because some of the organizations or offices already set up, they have only needed male staff, in some schools also. Some people and society have a prejudice man are the best than women. These types of thinking also reduce the chance of women. People thinking about women transportation difficulty, their maternity problems, family issues and night shifts as per these reasons people deliberately limit the opportunities for women. Some organizations think men are highly skilled than women, this is why women are neglected in the workplace.

- **Lack of Experience**

Lack of experience is another cause of unemployment. Because, every institutions and organizations are searching for experienced employees no one needs fresher has or newly graduated one. Organizations and institutions should consider the newly educated one; especially

for women; otherwise, they will not get opportunity to do jobs. Until, they are less experienced one.

- **Lack of Accommodation**

In case of women, she always is bothering about her safety. Therefore, while selecting the job opportunities she should look have there any hostel or accommodation facility. If it is not available, she will reject the job or resign from the job. It is the main reason for rejecting the jobs in remote areas.

- **More Interest in Youth Icons**

Today, all over the world searching for youth employees, especially in technical field, newly educated one are more active in technological skill. Therefore, this thing reduces the chance of less technical skill workers. Because, today the world under the technology. Moreover, the youth icons are highly flexible, creative, fantabulous workers, idealistic and so on. As per these reasons, they are one-step forward than the old generations.

- **Less Scope**

Now, the job is like a competition and the number of students completed the course is very high. By the reason, it will reduce the scope of a profession. Because, around the society have only limited vacancies and that also very competitive. Now it going on the high explosion of a single job. It will deduce the scope of that profession.

- **Stress**

Every job has its own stress. There are many causes of stress. Men and women share many of the same sources of stress, such as money, job security, health, and relationship issues. Perhaps a little more unique to women are the many roles they take on. In today's society, women's role often includes family obligations, caregiving children and/ or elderly parent and work responsibilities as well as other roles. As demands increase to fulfil these roles, women can fell overwhelmed with time pressure and unmet obligations. They may feel a sense of failure in not being able to meet expectations for themselves and others. Oftentimes women spend more time

meeting the needs of others rather than nurturing their own needs if functioning at high stress levels, women may not even recognize what their needs are.

Part 2: Solutions Suggested by the Professionally Qualified Unemployed Women.

Form a grievance cell or complaints committee. With this kind of investigation committee, women employees feel secure at workplaces. Besides, management should organize education campaigns for women employees to help them know their rights. The committee should listen to the complaints of women employee and investigate independently, keeping the identity of the employee under wrap. Moreover, proper working conditions should be provided for women. The employers should make the women employees feel easy, to come to them to share their workplace problems. Then, proper security should be provided for women, this is one of the most important factors, which needs to be taken care of well by the employers. Besides, providing a safe cab facility they have to ensure that women employees do not work late hours. Another most important thing is to provide awareness class for family members; through this program, they can change the negative attitude towards women and their job.

Women should be given a chance to express their feelings, it must encourage the female employees to express and come out of their discomfort. This can be done by boosting their confidence by implementing equal opportunities for both male and female workers in the workplace. These senses of equality in the workplace will make them fight the social stigma. Government should take care about women to ensure women safety in public and in their organizations, and should implement some laws with regards to women safety apart from implementing laws to ensure jobs for women. In addition, equal payment for both men and women should be ensured. Provide transportation facilities to ensure the security women. It is the responsibility of organizations, society and government. Provide all amenities for women without any discrimination.

- **Forming a Grievance Cell or Complaints Committee**

The committee will listen to the complaints of women employee and investigate independently, keeping the identity of the employee under wrap. The usefulness of this kind of committee is very relevant sexual harassment cases. With this kind of investigation committee,

women employees feel secure at workplaces. Besides, management should organize education campaigns for women employees to help them no their right issues.

• **Appropriate Work Condition**

Employers should try to give suitable work situation to women to make sure that there is no unfriendly atmosphere for the female workers. The employers should make the women employees feel easy, to come to them to share their workplace problems.

• **Proper Security**

This is one of the most important factors, which areas needed to be taken care of well by the employers. Besides, providing a safe cab facility they have to ensure that women employees do not work late hours. If in case, she needs to stay back to complete work, the office authority should take extra care of her security and safety. Giving sufficient maternity leaves and day care conveniences for working moms is something that employers should do to create a better work environment for women.

• **Provide Awareness for Family Members**

To provide proper awareness camp/ classes about the women education, their social status in society, employment opportunities for educated unemployed women. Due to this type of programs may change the negative attitude in to women employment.

• **Provide more Opportunities for Women**

Give more opportunities for women, through special post. That should be more attentive. It would reduce the unemployment. Appoint each of the women as per their qualification without any bias.

• **Be Capable of Coping with Problems**

Give motivational classes the educated women also, and be making them to coping with problems. It will help the women to survive the difficult situations in their life and in their profession. It makes the women more confident. Confident make the women think logically and independently. If have much confidence it will leads to high success in everyone's life.

• **Ensure Security of Women**

Ensure security of women; provide them a secure feeling in their offices. Moreover, to create awareness among the employees on women's safety and their health is vital. Use all possible techniques and ideas to spread awareness. Workshops, open group discussions or activities can help to create awareness on women's safety in the workplace. Awareness starts with the implementation of guidelines, and law against sexual harassment in a workplace.

• **Encourage Women to Express**

Generally, women's facing sexual harassment does not speak up. Society is responsible for this. We teach our girl child to behave and act in a particular way. Since childhood, we give them a set of do's and don'ts. This conditioning later stops women to express. They are ashamed. They fear consequences. Other reasons are low self-esteem and lack of information. Must encourage the female employees to express and come out their discomfort. This can be done by boosting their confidence by implementing equal opportunities for both male and female workers in the workplace. These senses of equality in the workplace will make them fight the social stigma.

• **Implementation of Laws**

Government should chart the statistics of women unemployment in every year. In addition, government should establish some laws favour to women for their employment. Should define the post for women. Government should bring strict decision on that. This can reduce the most of the women unemployment.

• **Provide Awareness about the Importance of Job**

Some of the women are not aware about the seriousness of job. They have only needed the degree certificates. First should give awareness to the educated one, they are the reason of unemployment. They have no idea about the importance of job, they do not know job will give them high status in society, it gives them earnings to live, it will give them high reputation and status in their family and society etc. Through the awareness classes, it will help to reduce some certain extent. Provide proper awareness camp about the education and employment opportunities for educated women.

• **Provide Basic Facilities for Women Employees**

Provide basic facilities for women employees. It does not mean the toilet facility or drinking facility, more than that, it means transportation facility and hostel facility also. Offices should provide travelling facility for employees at their own (company) risk. Institutions should organize the transportation facility and appoint special driver to drive women home at night. In addition, provide hostel facilities nearby their offices, with security protection. It will help to women avoid the night travelling it will consider more safety of women.

• **Create Positive Atmosphere in Family**

Create positive atmosphere from family onwards. It will make the women more relaxation in their mind, and it will make the job easy. Because, family is the first preference to women. It will be ok then everything will be ok.

• **Equal Pay for Equal Work**

It is the concept of labour rights that individuals in the same workplace be given equal pay. Provide equal pay for equal work, not only equal salary including basic pay, non-salary payments, bonuses and allowances. This for avoid gender discrimination. Because women also the part of society.

• **Avoid Gender Discrimination**

Support women into more senior roles; implement gender neutral recruitment processes, review salaries and standardized pay, provide training on unconscious bias.

• **Choose Fresher's**

Choose the newly educated one rather than the experienced person. This opportunity will give a way to new generations. It will help to acquaint with their jobs with new experience.

• **Provide Opportunity**

Provide opportunities especially for women, without any discrimination. To provide effective job-oriented training, government should support support to enhance the employment opportunities

• Take a Personal Interest

A personal interest should be needed to get job. It will not be happens without interest. Otherwise, if we have interest in to do jobs, it will make new rhythm of life.

• Bring Changes in Society Norms

Just try to understand the people about role of women, status of women in society and their rights and duties. Maybe it brings changes in society attitude towards women. Women is the part of the society; they have their own likes and dislikes. So, make a way for them to live freely and happily.

• Create Discussion Groups

Women discussion groups should organize at the village level.

• Self-Support Programs

Provide self-support programs effectively among educated unemployed women.

• Promote Additional Education

To promote additional educational qualification to the women

References

- Arjumand, T. (2016). Why is education important for girls? Retrieved from <https://www.qoura.com/why-is-education-so-important-for-girls>.
- Arun, S. (2017). An enquiry on the factors which retard the employment generation for educated youth in Kerala. *Kerala Institute of Labour and Employment, Trivandrum*.
- Duarte, L. (2016). How education is important. Retrieved from <https://content.wisestep.com/education-Important-top-reasons>
- Education statistics at a glance (2016) New Delhi: MHRD. Government of India
- Reddy, k. (2016). Reasons why women should work. Retrieved from <https://content.wisestep.com/top-good-reasons-why-women-should-work/>.
- Routray, S. (2016). A critical analysis of the gendered unemployment among educated women in India. *National journal of advanced research*, 2 (4), 09-11.